

Super Star-products and Quasi-Hopf Superalgebras

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Abstract. The purpose of this paper is to show that the theory of quasi-triangular quasi-Hopf superalgebras and quasi-triangular Lie super bialgebras can be developed in terms of the super star-product on a Poisson Lie supergroup and that equivalent super star-products generate identical quasi-triangular quasi-Hopf superalgebras.

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1 Introduction

In recent years, much interest has been made in the study of the Lie superalgebras [1–5]. The q -deformation of finite dimensional semisimple complex Lie algebras led to the study of certain types of quasitriangular Hopf algebras, which in turn yielded interesting solutions of the quantum Yang-Baxter equation (QYBE) [6, 7]. Quantized enveloping super algebras associated with simple Lie superalgebras have been introduced in [8]. Quantum superalgebras appeared naturally when the quantum inverse scattering method was generalized to the super-systems [9]. Quantum supergroups have been investigated and developed in [10–13]. R-matrix related to quantum superalgebras have been considered in [14, 15] and simple examples have been presented in [16], while universal R-matrices for quantum groups associated to simple Lie superalgebras have been introduced in [17].

The super Lie bialgebras have been investigated in [18]. The latter structures play an important role in the integrable structure of AdS/CFT correspondence [19], as well as in Toda models on Lie superalgebras [20]. An universal quantization for Lie super-bialgebras has been given in [22], where the author proved that the Drinfeld-Jimbo type superalgebra associated to a classical Lie superalgebra of type $A - G$ with distinguished Cartan matrix is isomorphic to the Etingof-Kazhdan quantization of the Lie superalgebra. The mathematical

features of the Hopf superalgebras emerging in the context of certain integrable models of theoretical physics has been presented in [21]. A classification of low-dimensional Lie super-bialgebras and their quantization in order to obtain quantum groups has been discussed in [23]. The classification of all two- and three-dimensional Lie super-bialgebras has been investigated in [24, 25] and the classical r -matrices of these Lie super-bialgebras and the super Poisson structures on the related Poisson-Lie supergroups have been developed in [26].

It is well-known that quantum groups can be seen as noncommutative generalizations of topological spaces, which have a group structure. Such a structure induces an abelian Hopf algebra structure [27] on the algebra of smooth functions on the group. The quantum groups [6, 7] are defined then as a non abelian Hopf algebras [28, 29]. A way to generate them consists of deforming the abelian Hopf algebra of functions into a non abelian one ($*$ -product), using the so-called deformation quantization or star-quantization [30–36]. A star-quantization method has been used also to give a deformed Yangian algebra $Y_F(g)$ associated to a simple Lie algebra in [37] and to develop a theory of well-behaved topological quantum algebras in [38].

The deformation quantization has been used extensively to study string theory D-branes in non-constant B-fields and more general curved backgrounds [39], supermembrane models [40], the fuzzy sphere [41] and BRST symmetry in quantum field theories [42]. The notion of a super star-product on a symplectic flat supermanifold has been investigated in [43]. The deformation quantization of certain Poisson brackets in the context of Batchelor supermanifolds using Fedosov's approach has been done by M. Bordemann [44, 45]. A generalization of Fedosov deformation-quantization to superspace has been proposed in [46]. The theories of triangular Hopf superalgebra developed in terms of a super star-product on a Poisson Lie supergroup has been investigated in [47]. In the works [48, 49], the integrals on Hopf superalgebras with special consideration of the Hopf superalgebras of regular functions on quantum or classical Lie supergroups [50] have been investigated.

The structures of quasi-Hopf superalgebras has been introduced in [51–53] as generalization of Drinfeld quasi-Hopf algebras [54, 55]. The main feature of quasi-Hopf superalgebras is an invertible even element Φ obeying a certain pentagon condition. These new structures give rise to new (non-standard) representations of the braid group and the corresponding link polynomials. In works [56–59], it has been shown that quasi-Hopf superalgebras are directly relevant to the elliptic quantum (super)groups [60, 61]. Basic statements about duality of Z_2 -graded Hopf algebras, and quasitriangular Z_2 -graded Hopf algebras have been detailed in [62].

The aim of this paper is to show that the quasi-Hopf superalgebras can be generated by deforming the graded (abelian) Hopf algebra of super functions structure into a non-graded abelian one (super star-product). This quantization technique

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gives a deformed product once a Poisson superbracket on the superalgebra of super smooth functions is given.

This paper is organized as follows. As a first step we wish to present in the next section (Section 2) some properties of the Lie bisuperalgebras, Poisson Lie supergroups, quantized universal enveloping superalgebras and Poisson Lie superalgebras on the complex number field. Section 3 is devoted to a review of some definitions of quasi-Hopf superalgebras given in [51, 52]. The notion of a super star-product on a Poisson Lie supergroups is explicitly defined in Section 4. Using the duality procedure, we show the main result of this paper, which states that a super star-product on Poisson Lie supergroup leads to the structure of the quasi-Hopf superalgebra on the super quantized enveloping algebra of the Lie superalgebra corresponding to the above Lie supergroup G (Section 5) and a quasi Lie super bialgebra structure on the corresponding Lie superalgebra (Section 6). Finally, in (Section 7) we show that equivalent super star-products generate identical quantum quasi-Hopf superalgebras and identical quasi-Lie super bialgebras.

2 Basic Definitions

This section is devoted to introduce some definitions of the Lie bisuperalgebras, Poisson Lie supergroups, quantized universal enveloping superalgebras and Poisson Lie superalgebras.

Let us first recall some properties of the vector superspaces and Lie superalgebras on the complex number field. If \mathfrak{g} is a vector super space then $\mathfrak{g} = \mathfrak{g}_1 \oplus \mathfrak{g}_0$, where we refer to \mathfrak{g}_0 and \mathfrak{g}_1 as the even and odd subspaces of \mathfrak{g} respectively. We define the operator index

$$|\cdot|: \quad \mathfrak{g} \longrightarrow \{0, 1\}$$

for the homogeneous elements of \mathfrak{g} by

$$|X| = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } X \in \mathfrak{g}_0 \\ 1 & \text{if } X \in \mathfrak{g}_1 \end{cases}$$

and call $(-1)^{|X|}$ the parity of X . The dual \mathfrak{g}^* inherits a natural super gradation $\mathfrak{g}^* = \mathfrak{g}_0^* \oplus \mathfrak{g}_1^*$, with \mathfrak{g}_a^* is isomorphic to the dual of \mathfrak{g}_a ($a = 0, 1$). On the tensor product $\mathfrak{g} \otimes \mathfrak{g}$, there exists a natural super gradation induced from that of \mathfrak{g} , where the parity of $x \otimes y$ is related to those of the homogenous elements $X, Y \in \mathfrak{g}$ through

$$(-1)^{|X \otimes Y|} = (-1)^{|X|+|Y|}.$$

It is also useful to define the twisting map

$$\tau : \mathfrak{g} \otimes \mathfrak{g} \longrightarrow \mathfrak{g} \otimes \mathfrak{g}$$

by

$$\tau(X \otimes Y) = (-1)^{|X||Y|}(Y \otimes X) \quad (1)$$

for all homogenous $X, Y \in \mathfrak{g}$; this definition is extended by linearity to all $\mathfrak{g} \otimes \mathfrak{g}$.

We now give the following definitions:

Definition 1. A Lie superalgebra structure on \mathfrak{g} is provided by a linear mapping

$$[\cdot, \cdot] : \mathfrak{g} \otimes \mathfrak{g} \longrightarrow \mathfrak{g}$$

satisfying the requirement of super Jacobi identity and super antisymmetry.

In order to express the requirement of a Lie superalgebra structure it is useful to introduce a basis $\{X_i\}$ in \mathfrak{g} and structure constants defined by $[X_i, X_j] = C_{ij}^k X_k$.

Definition 2. A Lie super-bialgebra structure on \mathfrak{g} is given by a linear mapping

$$\delta : \mathfrak{g} \longrightarrow \mathfrak{g} \otimes \mathfrak{g}$$

$$\delta(X_i) = \hat{C}_i^{kl} X_k \otimes X_l,$$

where δ has to satisfy several requirements. First of all it makes the dual linear space \mathfrak{g}^* a Lie superalgebra, i.e:

$$\hat{C}_k^{ij} = 0, \text{ whenever } |X_i| + |X_j| \neq |X_k| \pmod{2}$$

and

$$(-1)^{|X_k||X_m|} \hat{C}_i^{kj} \hat{C}_j^{lm} + (-1)^{|X_l||X_k|} \hat{C}_i^{lj} \hat{C}_j^{mk} + (-1)^{|X_m||X_l|} \hat{C}_i^{mj} \hat{C}_j^{kl} = 0.$$

δ must be a superalgebra 1-cocycle

$$\delta[X, Y] = ad_X \delta(Y) - (-1)^{|X||Y|} ad_Y \delta(X).$$

Definition 3. A coboundary Lie super-bialgebra is a pair (\mathfrak{g}, r) , where \mathfrak{g} is a Lie superalgebra and r an even element $\in ((\mathfrak{g}_0 \otimes \mathfrak{g}_0) \oplus (\mathfrak{g}_1 \otimes \mathfrak{g}_1))$, such that for every $X_i \in \mathfrak{g}$, we have

$$\delta(X_i) = [r, 1 \otimes X_i + X_i \otimes 1].$$

The even element r satisfies the generalized classical Yang-Baxter equation

$$[[r, r], 1 \otimes X_i \otimes 1 + X_i \otimes 1 \otimes 1 + 1 \otimes 1 \otimes X_i] = 0, \quad (2)$$

where the super Schouten $[[r, r]]$ bracket is defined as follows

$$[[r, r]] = [r_{12}, r_{13}] + [r_{12}, r_{23}] + [r_{13}, r_{23}].$$

and if we denote $r = r^{ij} X_i \otimes X_j$, then $r_{12} = r^{ij} X_i \otimes X_j \otimes 1$, $r_{13} = r^{ij} X_i \otimes 1 \otimes X_j$, $r_{23} = r^{ij} 1 \otimes X_i \otimes X_j$

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Definition 4. Quasi-triangular Lie super-bialgebras [18]: *If the even element r is a super skew-symmetric solution of the modified CYBE (generalized classical Yang-Baxter equation)*

$$[[r, r]] = \omega \quad \omega \in \wedge^3 \mathfrak{g}, \quad (3)$$

then the coboundary Lie super-bialgebra is said to be quasi-triangular.

Definition 5. A quantized universal enveloping (QUE) superalgebra H is a topologically free Hopf superalgebra over $\mathbf{C}[[\hbar]]$ such that $H/\hbar H$ is isomorphic as a Hopf superalgebra to $U(\mathfrak{g})$ for some Lie superalgebra \mathfrak{g} .

The following proposition was first given in the non-super case by Drinfeld [6] and latter proven in the super case by Andruskiewitsch [18].

Proposition 1. [18, 22] *Let H be a QUE superalgebra: $H/\hbar H \cong U(\mathfrak{g})$. Then the Lie superalgebra \mathfrak{g} has a natural structure of a Lie super bialgebra defined by*

$$\delta(X) = \hbar^{-1}(\Delta(\tilde{X}) - \Delta^{op}(\tilde{X})) \text{mod } \hbar, \quad X \in \mathfrak{g} \quad (4)$$

where $\tilde{X} \in H$ is a preimage of X and $\Delta^{op} := \tau \circ \Delta$.

Thereafter, let $M = M_0 + M_1$ be a differential supermanifold [64] and $F(M) = F_0(M) \oplus F_1(M)$ be the algebra of supersmooth functions on M ; $\phi_1 \in F_0(M)[F_1(M)]$ is said to be homogenous of even [odd] parity.

Definition 6. A super Poisson bracket $\{, \}$ on $F(M)$ is a bilinear operation assigning to every pair of functions $\{\phi_1, \phi_2\} \in F(M)$ a new function $\phi_1, \phi_2 \in F(M)$, such that for homogenous functions satisfies the following conditions:

i-Graded preserving

$$|\{\phi_1, \phi_2\}| = |\phi_1| + |\phi_2| \quad (5)$$

ii-Super skew-symmetry

$$\{\phi_1, \phi_2\} = -(-1)^{(|\phi_1||\phi_2|)} \{\phi_2, \phi_1\} \quad (6)$$

iii-Graded Leibniz rule

$$\{\phi_1, \phi_2 \phi_3\} = \{\phi_1, \phi_2\} \phi_3 + (-1)^{|\phi_1||\phi_2|} \phi_2 \{\phi_1, \phi_3\} \quad (7)$$

iv-Super Jacobi identity

$$\begin{aligned} & (-1)^{|\phi_1||\phi_3|} \{\phi_2, \{\phi_1, \phi_3\}\} \\ & + (-1)^{|\phi_2||\phi_1|} \{\phi_2, \{\phi_3, \phi_1\}\} \\ & + (-1)^{|\phi_3||\phi_2|} \{\phi_3, \{\phi_1, \phi_2\}\} = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Since the conditions [5-8] are just the axioms of superalgebras, the space $F(M)$ endowed with the super Poisson bracket becomes a Poisson superalgebra and M a Poisson supermanifold.

Definition 7. A Poisson Lie supergroup is a Lie supergroup G provided with a Poisson superbracket $\{\cdot, \cdot\}$ such that the comultiplication

$$\Delta : F(G) \longrightarrow F(G) \otimes F(G)$$

is a morphism of Poisson superbrackets:

$$\Delta\{\phi, \psi\} = \{\Delta(\phi), \Delta(\psi)\},$$

where the Poisson superbracket on $F(G) \otimes F(G)$ is defined as

$$\{\phi_1 \otimes \psi_1, \phi_2 \otimes \psi_2\} = (-1)^{|\phi_2||\psi_1|}(\{\phi_1, \phi_2\} \otimes \psi_1 \psi_2 + \phi_1 \phi_2 \otimes \{\psi_1, \psi_2\}). \quad (9)$$

and the following rule for the multiplication of graded tensor products should be used:

$$(\psi_1 \otimes \psi_2)(\phi_1 \otimes \phi_2) = (-1)^{|\psi_2||\phi_1|}(\psi_1 \phi_1 \otimes \psi_2 \phi_2)$$

3 Quasi-Hopf Superalgebras

In this section, we assume that K of characteristic zero and recall the following definitions [51, 52]

Definition 8. A quasi-superbialgebra is a \mathbf{Z}_2 graded unital associative algebra H over a field K which is equipped with algebra homomorphisms $\Delta : H \rightarrow H \otimes H$ (co-product), $\epsilon : H \rightarrow K$ (co-unit) and an invertible homogeneous element $\Phi \in H \otimes H \otimes H$ (co-associator) satisfying

$$(1 \otimes \Delta)\Delta(a) = \Phi^{-1}(\Delta \otimes 1)\Delta(a)\Phi, \quad \forall a \in H, \quad (10)$$

$$(\Delta \otimes 1 \otimes 1)\Phi \cdot (1 \otimes 1 \otimes \Delta)\Phi = (\Phi \otimes 1) \cdot (1 \otimes \Delta \otimes 1)\Phi \cdot (1 \otimes \Phi), \quad (11)$$

$$(\epsilon \otimes 1)\Delta = 1 = (1 \otimes \epsilon)\Delta, \quad (12)$$

$$(1 \otimes \epsilon \otimes 1)\Phi = 1. \quad (13)$$

It easy to show that the relations(11), (12) and (13) imply that Φ also obeys

$$(\epsilon \otimes 1 \otimes 1)\Phi = 1 = (1 \otimes 1 \otimes \epsilon)\Phi. \quad (14)$$

Since the co-associator Φ is homogenous, the co-unit proprieties imply that Φ is even and $|\Phi| = 0$

Definition 9. A quasi-Hopf superalgebra is a quasi-superbialgebra $(H, \Delta, \epsilon, \Phi)$ equipped with a super-algebra anti-homomorphism $S : H \rightarrow H$ (antipode) and canonical elements $\alpha, \beta \in H$, such that

$$m \cdot (1 \otimes \alpha)(S \otimes 1)\Delta(a) = \epsilon(a)\alpha, \quad \forall a \in H, \quad (15)$$

$$m \cdot (1 \otimes \beta)(1 \otimes S)\Delta(a) = \epsilon(a)\beta, \quad \forall a \in H, \quad (16)$$

$$m \cdot (m \otimes 1) \cdot (1 \otimes \beta \otimes \alpha)(1 \otimes S \otimes 1)\Phi^{-1} = 1, \quad (17)$$

$$m \cdot (m \otimes 1) \cdot (S \otimes 1 \otimes 1)(1 \otimes \alpha \otimes \beta)(1 \otimes 1 \otimes S)\Phi = 1. \quad (18)$$

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where m denotes the usual product map on \mathbb{H} : $m \cdot (a \otimes b) = ab$, which satisfies $m \cdot (m \otimes 1) = m \cdot (1 \otimes m)$.

For the homogeneous elements $a, b \in \mathbb{H}$, the antipode satisfies

$$S(ab) = (-1)^{|a||b|} S(b)S(a), \quad (19)$$

which extends to inhomogeneous elements through linearity.

Applying ϵ to definition (17, 18) we obtain, in view of (13), $\epsilon(\alpha)\epsilon(\beta) = 1$. It follows that the canonical elements α, β are both even. By applying ϵ to (15), we have $\epsilon(S(a)) = \epsilon(a)$, $\forall a \in \mathbb{H}$.

Now let $(\mathbb{H}, \Delta, \epsilon, \Phi)$ be a quasi-Hopf superalgebra, with α, β, S satisfying (15)-(18), and let $F \in \mathbb{H} \otimes \mathbb{H}$ be an invertible homogeneous element satisfying the co-unit properties

$$(\epsilon \otimes 1)F = 1 = (1 \otimes \epsilon)F. \quad (20)$$

It follows that F is even. We set

$$\Delta_F(a) = F\Delta(a)F^{-1}, \quad \forall a \in \mathbb{H}, \quad (21)$$

$$\Phi_F = (F \otimes 1)(\Delta \otimes 1)F \cdot \Phi \cdot (1 \otimes \Delta)F^{-1}(1 \otimes F^{-1}). \quad (22)$$

Then we have the following theorem:

Theorem 1. [51, 52] $(\mathbb{H}, \Delta_F, \epsilon, \Phi_F)$ defined by (21, 22) together with α_F, β_F, S_F given by

$$S_F = S, \quad \alpha_F = m \cdot (1 \otimes \alpha)(S \otimes 1)F^{-1}, \quad \beta_F = m \cdot (1 \otimes \beta)(1 \otimes S)F, \quad (23)$$

is also a quasi-Hopf superalgebra.

Definition 10. [51, 52] A quasi-Hopf superalgebra $(\mathbb{H}, \Delta, \epsilon, \Phi)$ is called quasi-triangular if there exists an invertible homogeneous element $R \in \mathbb{H} \otimes \mathbb{H}$, such that

$$\Delta^\tau(a)R = R\Delta(a), \quad \forall a \in \mathbb{H}, \quad (24)$$

$$(\Delta \otimes 1)R = \Phi_{231}^{-1}R_{13}\Phi_{132}R_{23}\Phi_{123}^{-1}, \quad (25)$$

$$(1 \otimes \Delta)R = \Phi_{312}R_{13}\Phi_{213}^{-1}R_{12}\Phi_{123}, \quad (26)$$

where $\Delta^\tau = \tau \cdot \Delta$ with τ being the graded twist map, and $\Phi_{132}, \Phi_{312}, \Phi_{231}$ are obtained from $\Phi \equiv \Phi_{123}$ with the help of the twist map τ .

It is easily shown that the properties (24)–(26) imply that the homogeneous element $R \in \mathbb{H} \otimes \mathbb{H}$ gratifies the following graded Yang-Baxter type equation:

$$R_{12}\Phi_{231}^{-1}R_{13}\Phi_{132}R_{23}\Phi_{123}^{-1} = \Phi_{321}^{-1}R_{23}\Phi_{312}R_{13}\Phi_{213}^{-1}R_{12}, \quad (27)$$

and the co-unit properties of R :

$$(\epsilon \otimes 1)R = 1 = (1 \otimes \epsilon)R. \quad (28)$$

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Theorem 2. *If $(H, \Delta, \epsilon, \Phi, R)$ is a quasi-triangular quasi-Hopf superalgebra, then $(H, \Delta_F, \epsilon, \Phi_F, R_F)$ is also a quasi-triangular quasi-Hopf superalgebra, with R_F given by*

$$R_F = F^\tau R F^{-1}, \quad (29)$$

where $F^\tau = \tau \cdot F \equiv F_{21}$. Here Δ_F and Φ_F are given by (21) and (22), respectively.

4 Super Star-Products on Poisson Lie Supergroups

In this section, we give basic statements concerning super star-products on Poisson Lie supergroups. Then let $G = G_0 \oplus G_1$ be a Lie supergroup, \mathfrak{g} its Lie superalgebra [1, 4, 5]. The enveloping algebra of the Lie superalgebra \mathfrak{g} is defined [63] to be the tensor algebra $T(\mathfrak{g}) = \bigoplus_{k=0}^{\infty} \mathfrak{g}^{\otimes k}$, modulo the ideal I in $T(\mathfrak{g})$ generated by all elements in $T(\mathfrak{g})$ of the form

$$X \otimes Y - (-1)^{|X||Y|} Y \otimes X - [X, Y] \quad (30)$$

for $X, Y \in \mathfrak{g}$. Let 1 be the identity of the enveloping superalgebra. Then the morphism of degree zero \mathfrak{g} into $U(\mathfrak{g}) \otimes U(\mathfrak{g})$ given by $X \rightarrow X \otimes 1 + 1 \otimes X$ extends to a morphism of degree zero which preserves the parity

$$\Delta_0 : U(\mathfrak{g}) \rightarrow U(\mathfrak{g}) \otimes U(\mathfrak{g}). \quad (31)$$

The antipode of the enveloping superalgebra is defined as an homogenous bijective map of degree zero

$$S_0 : U(\mathfrak{g}) \rightarrow U(\mathfrak{g}) \quad (32)$$

such that for any $X \in \mathfrak{g}$ we have

$$S_0(X) = -X \quad (33)$$

and for $X, Y \in U(\mathfrak{g})$ we have

$$S_0(XY) = (-1)^{|X||Y|} S_0(Y)S_0(X). \quad (34)$$

Now let $r \in ((\mathfrak{g}_0 \otimes \mathfrak{g}_0) \oplus (\mathfrak{g}_1 \otimes \mathfrak{g}_1))$ be a solution of the super generalized Yang-Baxter equation

$$[[r, r], 1 \otimes X_i \otimes 1 + X_i \otimes 1 \otimes 1 + 1 \otimes 1 \otimes X_i] = 0,$$

such that $r_{12} + r_{21}$ is a \mathfrak{g} invariant element of $\mathfrak{g} \otimes \mathfrak{g}$ and

$$[[r, r]] = \omega, \quad \text{where } \omega \in \wedge^3 \mathfrak{g}.$$

Let also t be an even invariant super-symmetric element of $\mathfrak{g} \otimes \mathfrak{g}$, i.e. an element $t = \sum_k a_k \otimes b_k$ such that $|a_k| = |b_k|$ for all k ,

$$\tau(t) = t; \text{ and}$$

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$$[X \otimes 1 + 1 \otimes X, t] = 0, \text{ for all } X \in \mathfrak{g}.$$

the even element t can be given in terms of the Casimir element $C = r + \tau(r)$ of \mathfrak{g} by the equality

$$t = C = r + \tau(r). \quad (35)$$

So, the Lie super bialgebra structure on the super algebra \mathfrak{g} is given by the superalgebra 1-cocycle

$$\begin{aligned} \delta : \mathfrak{g} &\longrightarrow \mathfrak{g} \otimes \mathfrak{g} \\ X &\longmapsto (ad_X \otimes 1 + 1 \otimes ad_X)r, \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

where ad_X stands for the adjoint representation and the super Poisson-Lie structure on Lie supergroup G is given by

$$\{\phi, \psi\} = \sum_{i,j} (-1)^{|\phi||j|} r^{ij} (X_i^r(\phi)X_j^r(\psi) - X_i^l(\phi)X_j^l(\psi)), \quad (37)$$

where $X_i^r = (R_g)_*X_i$ and $X_i^l = (L_g)_*X_i$ are the right and left vectors fields on the supergroup G , (X_i) is a basis of \mathfrak{g} with $(R_g)_*$ and $(L_g)_*$ the derivative mapping corresponding to the right and left translation respectively.

If we denote by $R(G)(L(G))$ the set of all right(left)-invariant vector fields on G , then using elementary properties of derivative mappings [64] one may show that each of $L(G)$ and $R(G)$ is a vector superspace with a bracket operation that satisfies the super Jacobi identity.

The action of $U(\mathfrak{g})$ on $\mathbf{F}(G)$ will be given by

$$\langle X, Y^l(\phi) \rangle = \langle XY, \phi \rangle \quad (38)$$

$$\langle X, Y^r(\phi) \rangle = (-1)^{|X||Y|} \langle S_0(Y)X, \phi \rangle. \quad (39)$$

We now make the following definitions

Definition 11. *A super star-product on the Poisson Lie supergroup is a bilinear map*

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{F}(G) \times \mathbf{F}(G) &\longrightarrow \mathbf{F}(G)[[h]] \\ (\phi, \psi) &\longmapsto \phi * \psi = \sum_j h^j C_j(\phi, \psi), \end{aligned}$$

such that

i) when the above map is extended to $\mathbf{F}(G)[[h]]$, it is formally associative

$$(\phi * \psi) * \chi = \phi * (\psi * \chi) \quad (40)$$

ii) $C_0(\phi, \psi) = \phi \cdot \psi = (-1)^{|\phi||\psi|} \psi \cdot \phi$

iii) $C_1(\phi, \psi) = \{\phi, \psi\}$

iv) the two-cochains $C_k(\phi, \psi)$ are bidifferential operators, homogeneous of degree zero on $\mathbf{F}(G)$.

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In this definition, the superalgebra $F(G)[[h]]$, with a new product $*$ and unchanged coproduct is considered to be Hopf superalgebra. We recall that deformations with unchanged coproduct are called preferred deformations [65].

The problem is to get a super star-product on the super group G such that the compatibility relation

$$\Delta(\phi * \psi) = (\Delta(\phi) * \Delta(\psi)) \quad (41)$$

is satisfied. The super star-product on the right side is canonically defined on $F(G) \otimes F(G)$ by

$$(\phi \otimes \psi) * (\phi' \otimes \psi') = (-1)^{|\psi||\phi'|} (\phi * \phi') \otimes (\psi * \psi'). \quad (42)$$

Definition 12. Two super star-products $*_1$ and $*_2$ defined on the supergroup G are said to be formally equivalent if there exists a series

$$T = id + \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} h^i T_i \quad (43)$$

where the T_i are even differential operators, such that

$$T(\phi *_1 \psi) = T(\phi) *_2 T(\psi). \quad (44)$$

If we introduce the homogeneous element of degree zero of $U(\mathfrak{g}) \otimes U(\mathfrak{g})[[h]]$

$$F = 1 + \frac{\hbar}{2} r + \sum_{i \geq 2} F_i h^i$$

Then we can give the following proposition:

Proposition 2. The super star-product on the Poisson Lie supergroup will be given by the following expression:

$$\phi * \psi = m((S_0^{\otimes 2})^{-1}(F^{-1})^r . F^l(\phi \otimes \psi)) \quad (45)$$

where m is the usual multiplication on the superalgebra of smooth functions on the supergroup. and $F^l(F)^r$ is the left (right) even bidifferential operator corresponding to the even element F , which satisfies the following equality

$$(\Delta_0 \otimes id)F(F \otimes 1) = \Phi(id \otimes \Delta_0)F(1 \otimes F) \quad (46)$$

where Φ is a even g -invariant element of $U(g)[[h]]^{\otimes 3}$

In fact, using the equations (38, 39) for any X in $U(g)[[h]]$, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle X, (\phi * \psi) * \chi \rangle &= \langle (F^{-1} \otimes 1) . (\Delta_0 \otimes 1) F^{-1} . (\Delta_0 \otimes id) \\ &\quad \Delta_0(X) . (\Delta_0 \otimes 1) F . (F \otimes 1), (\phi \otimes \psi \otimes \chi) \rangle. \end{aligned}$$

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In the same way, we obtain the following equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle X, \phi * (\psi * \chi) \rangle &= \langle (F^{-1} \otimes 1)(\Delta_0 \otimes 1)F^{-1}\Phi(id \otimes \Delta_0) \\ &\quad \Delta_0(X)\Phi^{-1}(\Delta_0 \otimes 1)F(F \otimes 1), (\phi \otimes \psi \otimes \chi) \rangle. \end{aligned}$$

The associativity of the super star-product defined in (45):

$$\phi * (\psi * \chi) = (\phi * \psi) * \chi$$

implies that the even element Φ gratifies the relation

$$\Phi(id \otimes \Delta_0)\Delta_0(X)\Phi^{-1} = (\Delta_0 \otimes id)\Delta_0(X); \quad (47)$$

or equivalently, for any $X \in \mathfrak{g} \subset \mathbf{U}(\mathfrak{g})$, we have the \mathfrak{g} -invariance of the even element Φ

$$[X \otimes 1 \otimes 1 + 1 \otimes X \otimes 1 + 1 \otimes 1 \otimes X, \Phi] = 0. \quad (48)$$

For the compatibility relation, the proof is a graded version of the proof given in [35].

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A super star-product does not only define a deformation of the superalgebra of the super smooth functions on the supergroup $\mathbf{F}(G)$ but also of a quotient superalgebra $\mathbf{F}_e(G)$ defined as the set of element of $\mathbf{F}(G)$ in a neighbour containing the identity of G modulo the equivalence relation

$$\phi \sim \psi \quad \text{if} \quad \langle X, \phi - \psi \rangle = 0 \quad \text{for any} \quad X \in U(\mathfrak{g}),$$

where \langle, \rangle is the pairing between $\mathbf{F}_e(G)$ and $U(\mathfrak{g})$.

The deformation of the $\mathbf{F}_e(G)$ as a super bialgebra allows us to provide by the duality the deformed superalgebra $\mathbf{F}_e^*(G)[[h]]$ where $\mathbf{F}_e^*(G)$ is the set of distributions on G with support at the unit element (e).

The super quantized enveloping algebra $U(\mathfrak{g})[[h]]$ is endowed with the structure of a Hopf superalgebra where the multiplication superalgebra is the ordinary convolution on $\mathbf{F}_e^*(G)$ and the coproduct Δ_F is given by [66]

$$\langle \Delta_F(X), \phi \otimes \psi \rangle = \langle X, \phi * \psi \rangle \quad (49)$$

for all $\phi, \psi \in \mathbf{F}_e(G)$, and $X \in U(\mathfrak{g})$

In fact using the equations (38,39) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \Delta_F(X), \phi \otimes \psi \rangle &= \langle X, \mu((S_0^{\otimes 2})^{-1}(F^{-1})^r.F^l(\phi \otimes \psi)) \rangle \\ &= \langle \Delta_0(X), (S_0^{\otimes 2})^{-1}(F^{-1})^r.F^l(\phi \otimes \psi) \rangle \\ &= \langle F^{-1}.\Delta_0(X).F, (\phi \otimes \psi) \rangle, \end{aligned}$$

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which implies that:

$$\Delta_F(X) = F^{-1}.\Delta_0(X).F. \quad (50)$$

and the associativity of the super star-product implies that the coproduct Δ_F satisfies the following equation:

$$(\Delta_F \otimes id)\Delta_F(X) = (id \otimes \Delta_F)\Delta_F(X). \quad (51)$$

In view of the equation (50), the latest equation (51) can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} (F^{-1} \otimes 1).(\Delta_0 \otimes id)(F^{-1}\Delta_0(X)F).(F \otimes 1) \\ = (1 \otimes F^{-1}).(id \otimes \Delta_0)(F^{-1}\Delta_0(X)F).(1 \otimes F) \end{aligned} \quad (52)$$

and using the fact that the even associator is given by

$$\Phi = (\Delta_0 \otimes id)F(F \otimes 1)(1 \otimes F^{-1})(id \otimes \Delta_0)F^{-1}, \quad (53)$$

we show that

$$(\Delta_0 \otimes id)\Delta_0(X) = \Phi(id \otimes \Delta_0)\Delta_0(X)\Phi^{-1} \quad (54)$$

or equivalently

$$\Phi^{-1}(\Delta_0 \otimes id)\Delta_0(X)\Phi = (id \otimes \Delta_0)\Delta_0(X), \quad (55)$$

which gives the first relation of the quasi-superbialgebra structure (10) and proves the \mathfrak{g} -invariance of the even element Φ . We show now that the even element Φ given by (53) defines completely a super quasi bialgebra structure on the super quantized enveloping algebra $(U(\mathfrak{g}[[\hbar]]), \varepsilon, \Delta_0)$.

Then, firstly, using the fact that $\phi * 1 = 1 * \phi = \phi$ for all $\phi \in \mathbf{F}_e(G)$, we deduce that

$$(id \otimes \varepsilon)F = (\varepsilon \otimes id)F = 1, \quad (56)$$

where ε is the usual co-unit of the enveloping algebra $U(g)$, which implies that the associator Φ satisfies

$$(id \otimes \varepsilon \otimes id)\Phi = (id \otimes id \otimes \varepsilon)\Phi = (\varepsilon \otimes id \otimes id)\Phi = 1; \quad (57)$$

Thereafter we prove that the associator Φ satisfies the pentagon equation

$$(\Delta_0 \otimes id \otimes id)\Phi(id \otimes id \otimes \Delta_0)\Phi = (\Phi \otimes 1)(id \otimes \Delta_0 \otimes id)\Phi(1 \otimes \Phi); \quad (58)$$

in fact

$$\begin{aligned} (\Delta_0 \otimes id \otimes id)\Phi(id \otimes id \otimes \Delta_0)\Phi \\ = (\Delta_0 \otimes id \otimes id)((\Delta_0 \otimes id)F(F \otimes 1)(1 \otimes F^{-1})(id \otimes \Delta_0)F^{-1}) \\ (id \otimes id \otimes \Delta_0)((\Delta_0 \otimes id)F(F \otimes 1)(1 \otimes F^{-1})(id \otimes \Delta_0)F^{-1}) \\ = (\Phi \otimes 1).(id \otimes \Delta_0 \otimes id)\Phi.(1 \otimes \Phi). \end{aligned}$$

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so, we deduce that the super quantized enveloping algebra $(U(\mathfrak{g}[[\hbar]], \Phi, \varepsilon, \Delta_0)$ is a \mathbf{Z}_2 graded quasi bialgebra.

The quasi-superbialgebra $(U(\mathfrak{g}[[\hbar]], \Delta_0, \Phi, \varepsilon)$ is a deformation of the Hopf superalgebra $U(\mathfrak{g})$, i.e, $U(\mathfrak{g}[[\hbar]])/h(U(\mathfrak{g}[[\hbar]])$ is isomorphic, as a quasi-Hopf superalgebra, to $(U(\mathfrak{g}))$. Therefore, there exists a homomorphism $S : U(\mathfrak{g}[[\hbar]]) \rightarrow U(\mathfrak{g}[[\hbar]])$ such that $(U(\mathfrak{g}[[\hbar]], \Delta_0, \Phi, \varepsilon, S)$ is a quasi-Hopf superalgebra.

To find the expression of the antipode of the super quantized enveloping algebra $(U(\mathfrak{g}[[\hbar]], \Delta_0, \Phi, \varepsilon, S)$, we recall first that the antipode S_0 of $U(\mathfrak{g})$ satisfies the following equation:

$$m(S_0 \otimes id)\Delta_0(X) = m(id \otimes S_0)\Delta_0(X) = \varepsilon(X)1,$$

where m is the usual multiplication on the super enveloping algebra $U(\mathfrak{g})$, and F and F^{-1} can be respectively split as

$$F = \sum_k a_k \otimes b_k, \quad F^{-1} = \sum_k c_k \otimes d_k$$

and if setting $u = m(id \otimes S_0)(F^{-1})$ as an invertible homogeneous element of $U(\mathfrak{g}[[\hbar]])$ of degree zero, then we can easily show that the antipode $S_F(X)$ of the super quantized enveloping algebra $U(\mathfrak{g}[[\hbar]])$ is given by:

$$S_F(X) = u.S_0(X).u^{-1}, \quad \text{where } u^{-1} = m(S_0 \otimes id)F.$$

Finally, by a direct computation detailed respectively in [47, 66], we show that S_F defines an antipode on the quantum super algebra $(U(\mathfrak{g}[[\hbar]], \Delta_F, \varepsilon)$ and consequently $(\alpha = \beta = 1, S_0)$ defines a quasi-Hopf super algebra structure on the super quasibialgebra $(U(\mathfrak{g}[[\hbar]], \Delta_0, \Phi, \varepsilon)$.

Now if we define the following even element, as Drinfeld does in [54, 55] for the non graded case

$$R_F = F_{21}^{-1}.e^{\frac{\hbar t}{2}}.F,$$

where $F_{21} = \tau.F_{12}.\tau$ and t be the even invariant super-symmetric element of $\mathfrak{g} \otimes \mathfrak{g}$ defined in (35).

Following the same approach as the non graded case [54, 55], we give the following theorem

Theorem 3. [22] *The quasitriangular Hopf superalgebra structure on the quantum superalgebra $(U(\mathfrak{g}[[\hbar]], \Delta_F, S_F, \varepsilon)$ is given by the element $R_F = (F_{21})^{-1}.e^{\frac{\hbar t}{2}}.F$ with satisfies the following equalities:*

$$(\Delta_F \otimes id)R_F = (R_F)_{13}.(R_F)_{23}. \tag{59}$$

$$(id \otimes \Delta_F)R_F = (R_F)_{13}.(R_F)_{12}. \tag{60}$$

$$(\Delta_F)^{op} = R_F.\Delta_F.(R_F)^{-1}. \tag{61}$$

In view of the equations ((59)-(60)-(61)) we show that the even element R_F satisfies the graded quantum Yang-Baxter equation

$$(R_F)_{12} \cdot (R_F)_{13} \cdot (R_F)_{23} = (R_F)_{23} \cdot (R_F)_{13} \cdot (R_F)_{12}. \quad (62)$$

For the quantized enveloping superalgebra $(U(\mathfrak{g}[[h]], \Delta_0, S_0, \varepsilon, \Phi)$ we have the following proposition:

Proposition 3. *The even element $R = e^{\frac{ht}{2}}$ defines a quasi-triangular quasi Hopf superalgebra structure on the quantized enveloping algebra $(U(\mathfrak{g}[[h]], \Delta_0, S_0, \varepsilon, \Phi)$ where t is an even invariant super-symmetric element of $\mathfrak{g} \otimes \mathfrak{g}$.*

In fact, from the relation $(id \otimes \Delta_F)R_F = (R_F)_{13} \cdot (R_F)_{12}$, we can derive that

$$\begin{aligned} (id \otimes \Delta_0)e^{\frac{ht}{2}} &= (id \otimes \Delta_0)(F_{21})(1 \otimes F)(F_{31}^{-1}e^{\frac{ht_{13}}{2}}F_{13}) \\ &\quad (F_{21}^{-1}e^{\frac{ht_{12}}{2}}(\Delta_0 \otimes id)F^{-1}\Phi_{123}) \end{aligned}$$

which gives the following equation:

$$(id \otimes \Delta_0)e^{\frac{ht}{2}} = \Phi_{312}e^{\frac{ht_{13}}{2}}\Phi_{213}^{-1}e^{\frac{ht_{12}}{2}}\Phi_{123} \quad (63)$$

in the same way, from the relation $(\Delta_F \otimes id)R_F = (R_F)_{13} \cdot (R_F)_{23}$, we deduce that

$$(\Delta_0 \otimes id)e^{\frac{ht}{2}} = \Phi_{231}^{-1}e^{\frac{ht_{13}}{2}}\Phi_{132}e^{\frac{ht_{23}}{2}}\Phi_{123}^{-1} \quad (64)$$

It is a simple matter of computation to show that the properties (63)-(64) imply that $R = e^{\frac{ht}{2}}$ satisfies the graded quasi-Yang-Baxter equation

$$e^{\frac{ht_{12}}{2}}\Phi_{231}^{-1}e^{\frac{ht_{13}}{2}}\Phi_{132}e^{\frac{ht_{23}}{2}}\Phi_{123}^{-1} = \Phi_{321}^{-1}e^{\frac{ht_{23}}{2}}\Phi_{312}e^{\frac{ht_{13}}{2}}\Phi_{213}^{-1}e^{\frac{ht_{12}}{2}}, \quad (65)$$

then we deduce that $R = e^{\frac{ht}{2}}$ defines a quasi-triangular quasi Hopf superalgebra structure on the quantized enveloping algebra $(U(\mathfrak{g}[[h]], \Delta_0, S_0, \varepsilon, \Phi)$.

To conclude we stress that we have established that a super star-product on the super Poisson-Lie group $(G = G_0 \oplus G_1, r)$ leads to a quasi-triangular quasi Hopf superalgebra structure on the quantized enveloping algebra $(U(\mathfrak{g}[[h]], \Delta_0, S_0, \varepsilon, \Phi, R)$ where $R = e^{\frac{ht}{2}}$ and $\Phi = (\Delta_0 \otimes id)F(F \otimes 1)(1 \otimes F^{-1})(id \otimes \Delta_0)F^{-1}$ with $F = 1 + \frac{h}{2}r + \sum_{i \geq 2} F_i h^i$ and $t = r + \tau(r)$.

6 Super Star-Products and Quasi-Lie Super Bi-Algebra

Using the fact that F defining the super star-product (45) can be decomposed as

$$F = 1 + \frac{h}{2}r + \sum_{i \geq 2} F_i h^i$$

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the associator given by the relation

$$\Phi = (\Delta_0 \otimes id)F(F \otimes 1)(1 \otimes F^{-1})(id \otimes \Delta_0)F^{-1}$$

can be decomposed as

$$\Phi = \Phi_2 + h^2\Phi_2 + \dots, \quad (66)$$

where $\Phi_1 = 0$ and $Alt\Phi_2 = -4\omega = -4[[r, r]]$ in fact for any even element $F = 1 + \frac{h}{2}r + \sum_{i \geq 2} F_i h^i \in (U(\mathfrak{g}))^{\otimes 2}[[h]]$; its inverse is given by the equality

$$F^{-1} = 1 - \frac{h}{2}r + \sum_{i \geq 2} \tilde{F}_i h^i,$$

where $\tilde{F}_k = -F_k + \sum_{l, j \geq 2; l+j=k} F_l \tilde{F}_j$.

From the equation (66) we deduce that

$$\Phi_1 = r_{12} + (\Delta_0 \otimes id)r - r_{23} + (id \otimes \Delta_0)r = r_{12} + (r_{23} + r_{13}) - r_{23} - (r_{13} + r_{12}) = 0$$

and a similar calculus show that

$$(\Phi_2)_{123} + (\Phi_2)_{231} + (\Phi_2)_{312} - (\Phi_2)_{213} - (\Phi_2)_{132} - (\Phi_2)_{321} = 4[[r, r]],$$

then we have the second result.

Proposition 4. *The quasi-Lie super bi-algebra structure on the superalgebra \mathfrak{g} corresponding to the Poisson Lie supergroup G is given by the triplet $(\mathfrak{g}, \delta, \gamma)$, where:*

$$\begin{aligned} \delta : \mathfrak{g} &\rightarrow \mathfrak{g} \otimes \mathfrak{g} \\ X &\rightarrow \delta(X) = [r, 1 \otimes X_i + X_i \otimes 1] \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\gamma = -\frac{1}{4}Alt(\Phi_2) = -[[r, r]].$$

From the \mathfrak{g} -invariance of Φ it can be seen that

$$[X \otimes 1 \otimes 1 + 1 \otimes X \otimes 1 + 1 \otimes 1 \otimes X, \gamma] = 0.$$

7 Equivalent Super Star-Products and Isomorphic Quasi-Hopf Superalgebras

Let F and \bar{F} be two super star-products i.e, two homogeneous elements of degree zero of the Hopf superalgebra $(U(\mathfrak{g})[[h]])$ and let $H = (U(\mathfrak{g})[[h]], \Delta_0, e^{\frac{h}{2}}, S_0, \Phi)$ and $\bar{H} = (U(\mathfrak{g})[[h]], \Delta_0, e^{\frac{h}{2}}, S_0, \bar{\Phi})$ the corresponding quasi-Hopf superalgebras, where

$$\Phi = (\Delta_0 \otimes id)F(F \otimes 1)(1 \otimes F^{-1})(id \otimes \Delta_0)F^{-1},$$

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$$\bar{\Phi} = (\Delta_0 \otimes id)\bar{F}(\bar{F} \otimes 1)(1 \otimes \bar{F}^{-1})(id \otimes \Delta_0)\bar{F}^{-1}.$$

If the two super star-product are equivalent, i.e. the corresponding even elements F and \bar{F} are related by the following expression:

$$\bar{F} = \Delta_0(E^{-1}).F.(E \otimes E) \quad (67)$$

for some invertible homogeneous element E of degree zero of $U(\mathfrak{g})[[\hbar]]$. The co-associator $\bar{\Phi}$ can be rewritten as $\bar{\Phi} = (\Delta_0 \otimes id)\bar{F}(\bar{F} \otimes 1)(1 \otimes \bar{F}^{-1})(id \otimes \Delta_0)\bar{F}^{-1}$
 $\bar{\Phi} = (\Delta_0 \otimes id)(\Delta_0(E^{-1}).(F \otimes 1))(1 \otimes F^{-1})(id \otimes \Delta_0)F^{-1}(id \otimes \Delta_0)\Delta_0(E)$. $\bar{\Phi} = (\Delta_0 \otimes id)\Delta_0(E^{-1}).\Phi.(id \otimes \Delta_0)\Delta_0(E)$. $\bar{\Phi} = \Phi$ which implies that equivalent super star-products generate only one quasi-triangular quasi-Hopf superalgebra and obviously only one quasi-lie super bialgebra.

If the super star-products are not equivalent then they generate two different quasi-Hopf superalgebras $(U(\mathfrak{g})[[\hbar]], \Phi, \Delta_0, e^{\frac{\hbar t}{2}})$ and $(U(\mathfrak{g})[[\hbar]], \Phi', \Delta_0, e^{\frac{\hbar t}{2}})$ which are isomorphic thanks to the following theorem which is a graded version of the one given by Drinfeld in [54, 55].

Theorem 4. Assume we have $H = (U(\mathfrak{g})[[\hbar]], \Phi, \Delta_0, e^{\frac{\hbar t}{2}})$ and $H' = (U(\mathfrak{g})[[\hbar]], \Phi', \Delta_0, e^{\frac{\hbar t}{2}})$, which are the quantum enveloping superalgebras of the same finite dimensional Lie superalgebra \mathfrak{g} then there exist a gauge transformation $F \in (U(\mathfrak{g})^{\otimes 2}[[\hbar]])$ such that $H' = H_F$.

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